

Using Digital Technology to Conduct COVID-19 Surveillance: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic has led to new ideas in surveillance, including the use of digital technology. However, there is limited knowledge about the role of digital technology in COVID-19, including its challenges.

Objectives: This study explored how digital technology supports COVID-19 surveillance and examined the challenges and opportunities associated with using these technologies.

Methodology: A systematic review was conducted using the Population Intervention Comparison and Outcome framework, analysing papers from the SCOPUS database. The study focused on the use of websites for COVID-19 surveillance during the pandemic.

Results: Digital technologies significantly contributed to virus surveillance through innovations like smartphone-based contact tracing, proximity tracking protocols, the Internet of Things (IoT), video monitoring technologies, and web-based applications. The deployment of digital technologies in response to emerging diseases such as COVID-19 has been hampered by a constellation of interrelated challenges. Key among these are (1) the scarcity of high-quality, unbiased data and the difficulties of integrating disparate datasets; (2) limitations in technology design and the shortage of skilled human resources to develop, deploy, and maintain digital tools; (3) gaps in physical and network infrastructure, particularly in low- and middle-income settings; (4) cybersecurity vulnerabilities and complex ethical quandaries around privacy, consent, and algorithmic transparency; and (5) broader political, social, and environmental barriers, ranging from governance misalignment to inequitable access and ecological impacts. Each of these

domains must be addressed holistically to ensure that digital interventions can effectively support surveillance, diagnosis, treatment, and prevention in future health emergencies.

Unique Contribution: This study emphasises the role of digital technologies in virus detection, monitoring, and prevention as a medium of infectious disease transmission, particularly in contact tracing, symptom monitoring, location tracking, and real-time data management. It highlights the challenges of privacy, data security, and public adoption issues.

Conclusion: Digital technology has demonstrated its pivotal role in strengthening public health surveillance during the pandemic, improving efficiency, accuracy, and capacity in pandemic response. Collaboration is needed between technology developers, policymakers, and efforts to enhance public digital literacy to maximise the benefits of technology in health surveillance.

Key Recommendation: Future research should focus on developing digital technology websites, particularly for the surveillance of other infectious diseases, such as monkeypox and foot-and-mouth disease.

Keywords: Pandemic, surveillance activities, digital technology, COVID-19 surveillance

Introduction

COVID-19 represents a public health disaster that exceeds the average capacity of existing health systems, necessitating immediate measures to prevent or mitigate its adverse effects on public health (Afolabi, 2018). The pandemic has particularly highlighted the fragility of health systems, which often lack adequate infrastructure, tools, policies, and organisational capacity to protect and promote public health. Effective disaster management is crucial to minimising losses and casualties and requires a comprehensive approach rooted in four key components: mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery (Coppola, 2011). The success of such management depends on the active participation of all stakeholders—governments, health agencies, volunteers, and the general public—in implementing measures to reduce risks.

The application of epidemiology in disaster situations, known as disaster epidemiology, provides policymakers, planners, incident commanders, decision-makers, and affected communities with critical and actionable insights (Malilay et al., 2014). Disaster epidemiologists play a vital role in conducting surveillance across all phases of disaster management: pre-disaster, emergency response, and post-disaster. Effective surveillance requires a robust infrastructure, including advanced information technology systems, skilled personnel, expertise in modern media communication, and strong political authority and support (Frieden et al., 2008). During the COVID-19 pandemic, surveillance efforts focused on suspected cases, close contacts, and confirmed cases, each necessitating an epidemiological investigation (PE) using a standardized three-page form, as outlined by the Indonesian Ministry of Health's guidelines (Indonesian Ministry of Health, 2020).

The extensive use of paper in PE for COVID-19, particularly in zoonotic disasters, increases costs and contributes to environmental waste. Zoonoses are diseases transmitted between animals and humans, caused by bacteria, fungi, viruses, or parasites such as protozoa and worms. Examples include COVID-19, Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD), the Nipah Virus, and monkeypox (UNDRR, 2019). For each confirmed COVID-19 case, the PE process requires completing a three-sheet form, especially when the patient is referred to a hospital or controlled isolation site. When patients are not referred, the forms are archived. Once the storage period for these records ends, the paper is discarded, contributing to environmental pollution. Moreover, the rising cost of paper adds to the financial burden. A sustainable solution to this issue is the digitization of PE forms, offering a more efficient and environmentally friendly alternative to paper-based documentation.

The development of web-based medical record documentation and applications for COVID-19 patients in health facilities, such as puskesmas (community health centres), clinics, and hospitals, remains limited. One example is the SIRCoVIT Klinik dr. Mulio Soreang. It is an application designed to facilitate the entry of general and COVID-19 patient data, document medical records, and generate reports (Rahayu et al., 2021). Another example is the Jogja Smart Service (JSS) app, used at Puskesmas Gondokusuman in Yogyakarta for patient registration (Eko et al., 2022). While many digital health applications for COVID-19 focus on patient registration and case tracking, few are specifically tailored for COVID-19 epidemiological surveillance. Currently, apps developed by the Indonesian Ministry of Health, such as Peduli Lindungi, SILACAK, Perisai, the COVID-19 Patient Information System, and HEALTH-M, serve as the primary tools for COVID-19 surveillance (Andriani & Fahmi, 2022).

The role of developing various digital health technology applications, especially during the pandemic, needs to be evaluated, primarily to assess the challenges of their implementation. This necessitates a systematic review to comprehensively collect, evaluate, and analyse the existing literature. Conducting this review to identify the role and challenges associated with digital technology utilisation is essential. Doing so aims to provide a deeper and more valuable understanding that can contribute to the scientific knowledge of digital technology in emerging disease surveillance.

Objectives of the Study

Based on this background, the systematic review aimed to:

1. Evaluate the role of digital technology in health surveillance during the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. Identify the challenges and opportunities associated with their implementation.

Methods

The study used the PICO (Population/Problem, Intervention, Comparison, Outcomes) Framework, developed by the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence, to systematically collect, select, extract, and analyze scientific articles relevant to the topic. The scope of the review was defined based on the structure of the research questions. The primary research question for this study is: *What is the role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance?* Specific restrictions on the study's scope are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Scope

Component	Description
<i>Population</i>	COVID-19 Surveillance
<i>Intervention</i>	Digital technology
<i>Comparison</i>	n/a
<i>Outcome</i>	Role of digital technology

Strategy of Search

The present study focuses on research on digital technologies used for disaster surveillance during the coronavirus pandemic (SARS-Cov-2) from 2020 to the present. Considering the scope and limited financial resources, the SCOPUS database was chosen as the primary source for analysis. SCOPUS is a good quality bibliometric data source, carefully curated for academic research in quantitative fields (Baas et al., 2019). Articles were searched using the keywords: 'Digital', 'Technology', 'Surveillance', and 'COVID-19'. The terms were combined to ensure a more targeted search, and the search was limited to articles published within the specified timeframe.

Publications that matched the search parameters on title, keywords, and/or abstract and met the inclusion criteria were selected for analysis.

Criteria of Inclusion and Exclusion

The literature sources were selected using the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. Articles were selected based on predetermined eligibility criteria, including inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were as follows: (1) scientific articles written in English or Indonesian, (2) literature in the form of scientific articles published in journals, (3) articles published between 2020 and 2023, and (4) articles that discuss digital technology for disaster surveillance in the context of the ongoing pandemic. The exclusion criteria were as follows: (1) scientific articles that were not available in full text, and (2) articles in the form of literature reviews. Articles that did not meet these criteria were excluded from this study.

Figure 1. Flowchart of Scientific Article Selection Process

Process of Selection Flow

Preliminary research results from a predefined database search showed that 212 articles and papers met the inclusion criteria. This initial search effectively excluded articles with repeated keyword

variants, thus ensuring a better selection. The article selection process is illustrated in Figure 1, which presents a flow chart detailing the steps taken during this process.

In the initial stage, the title and keywords of each publication were reviewed to assess their relevance to the role of digital technologies in COVID-19 surveillance. Based on the initial exclusion criteria, the first screening eliminated two documents. Subsequently, applying the second exclusion criterion removed an additional 127 documents, leaving 81 papers for further review. In the second stage, abstracts of the remaining documents were evaluated to determine their relevance to the role of digital technologies in COVID-19 surveillance. At this stage, 67 papers were eliminated, resulting in a final selection of 14 documents for further analysis and synthesis.

Results

In the initial stage, the title and keywords of each publication were reviewed to evaluate their relevance to the role of digital technologies in COVID-19 surveillance. The first stage of screening, based on the initial exclusion criteria, resulted in the elimination of 2 documents. After that, applying the second exclusion criterion resulted in an additional 127 papers being eliminated, leaving 81 documents for further consideration. In the second stage, abstracts of the remaining documents were assessed for their relevance to digital technologies in COVID-19 surveillance. This review eliminated 67 documents, resulting in 14 papers for further analysis and synthesis. Based on publication date, there were 1 article published in 2020, 3 articles published in 2021, 6 articles published in 2022, 2 articles published in 2023, and 1 article published in 2024 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Number of Published Articles during the Years 2020-2024

Author affiliations varied, with one article each written by researchers from educational institutions in Japan, China, India, and Spain. In addition, one study resulted from a collaboration between researchers in Canada and Australia. Regarding journal publications, the 15 articles were published in 13 different journals, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. List of Authors and Publication in a Journal

Document	Authors Country	Journal
Owusu (2020)	United Kingdom	Global Health Research and Policy
Chowdhury et al. (2020)	United States	IEEE Access
Hayati et al. (2021)	United Kingdom	International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications
Ummer et al. (2021)	United Kingdom	BMJ Global Health
Unruh et al. (2021)	United States	American Journal of Infection Control
Baik & Eugene (2022)	United States	Mobile Media and Communication

Geng & John (2022)	Cyprus	Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies
Sayibu, Jianxun, Tosin, Olatemi, et al. (2022)	United States	Digital Health
Sayibu, Jianxun, Akintunde, et al. (2022)	Netherlands	Smart Health
Surio et al. (2022)	United States	Public Health Reports
Louw (2023)	Canada	Journal of Medical Internet Research
Roberts & Ilan (2023)	United Kingdom	Global Public Health
O’Dwyer et al. (2024)	Canada	JMIR Public Health and Surveillance
Hsiao et al. (2024)	Canada	JMIR Public Health and Surveillance
	(a)	(b)

Of the 14 studies examined, 3 used a descriptive, general reflection, or theoretical approach; 8 used qualitative and quantitative methods through primary data collection; and 3 used a content analysis approach. Details regarding the types of articles and methodologies used are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Type of Article and Methodology Used

Authorship	Article Type*			Explanation of the Method
	A	B	C	
Owusu (2020)	X			This article offers recommendations for a privacy—and data-protection-focused regulatory framework for mobile applications (‘apps’) designed to notify individuals who may have been exposed to coronavirus and serve as an alternative to traditional contact tracing methods.
Chowdury et al. (2020)		X		We critically review COVID-19 contact tracing protocols and applications to identify their strengths and weaknesses. We offer recommendations for improving future contact tracing mechanisms to be more universally interoperable and privacy-preserving, thereby fostering digital trust and striking the right balance between privacy and data accuracy.
Hayati et al. (2021)		X		This article proposes a reference model for designing an active digital surveillance system for infectious diseases using Internet of Things (IoT) technology. The model consists of 14 attributes with specific indicators tailored to the unique characteristics of IoT, which fulfil the design requirements of infectious disease surveillance. A key use case of this model is a community-based surveillance system that leverages IoT to detect early symptoms and prevent close contact related to COVID-19 in nursing homes.
Ummer et al. (2021)		X		This article uses a global framework to explore the use of digital tools in Kerala across multiple domains, including communication, surveillance, clinical management, non-clinical support, and core health system preparedness and response.
Unruh et al. (2021)		X		This article discusses using video technology to improve case interviews, identify COVID-19 contacts, and assess exposure risks in a large juvenile temporary detention centre. The researchers developed a COVID-19 outbreak management

Authorship	Article Type*			Explanation of the Method
	A	B	C	
				protocol that includes establishing an outbreak management team and improving infection control through video surveillance.
Baik and Jang (2022)		X		How surveillance technologies are placed in horizontal and vertical relationships in people's daily lives to fully understand individual and societal acceptance and/or rejection of the system during the crisis.
Geng and John (2022)		X		An online survey with an exploratory research design to investigate how the COVID-19 pandemic has changed the use of Digital Mobile Technology (DMT) among 1,126 frontline healthcare practitioners in three leading tertiary hospitals in Ghana. The researchers used the Technology Acceptance Model to examine DMT adoption and utilisation and its limitations in COVID-19 management.
Sayibu, Jianxun, Tosin, Olatemi, et al. (2022)		X		Temperature thermometer detectors, mobile usability, and app familiarity enhance COVID-19 risk mitigation in high- and low-risk environments. Standardising data sets is critical to ensuring privacy and upholding data ethics and security. The authors conducted a cross-sectional survey to gain an in-depth understanding of risk mitigation, mobile temperature thermometer detectors, and other variables related to surveillance and monitoring among 850 university students and healthcare workers.
Sayibu, Jianxun, Akintunde, et al. (2022)		X		Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) to conceptualize the importance of mobile usability, mobile digital culture, knowledge of apps, and environmental conditions in COVID-19 mitigation. A cross-sectional method was used through an online survey to collect data from 459 mobile phone users. The relationships in the research model were assessed using structural equation modelling (Amos v.24.0).
Surio et al. (2022)	X			A consensus-based approach through monthly discussions with partners to categorise digital tools into five categories: surveillance systems, case investigation, proximity technology/exposure notification, contact tracing, and symptom tracking/monitoring. The most frequently used tools include the National Electronic Disease Surveillance System (NBS), Sara Alert, REDCap, and Maven. Some tools, such as NBS, Sara Alert, REDCap, Salesforce, and Microsoft Dynamics, are reused or adapted across different categories. Access to a publicly available inventory of digital technologies and tools equips public health officials and informatics leaders with insights into what tools are being used by other public health agencies, aiding in decision-making regarding the reuse of existing tools or the adoption of new tools.

Authorship	Article Type*			Explanation of the Method
	A	B	C	
Louw (2023)		X		Official websites of the Japanese and German governments were used to identify digital solutions developed and used for contact tracing during the COVID-19 pandemic between January and December 2021. A case-oriented comparative analysis was used to determine which solutions were published as open source.
Roberts and Ilan (2023)	X			This article critically examines approaches to conceptualising, understanding, and implementing digital health in the context of infectious disease outbreaks, drawing on insights from COVID-19 and previous examples. It examines ‘explicitly informal’ digital health by assessing the strengths and limitations of current practices in organizing digital health for infectious disease outbreaks. The review explores how digital responses to managing and regulating contagious disease outbreaks can be re-conceptualised, revisited, or revised.
O'Dwyer et al. (2024)		X		Guided by the Reach, Effectiveness, Adoption, Implementation, and Maintenance (RE-AIM) framework, researchers conducted an exploratory qualitative study to investigate the implementation and impact of Digital Contact Tracing (DCT) at Children's Hospital Eastern Ontario between December 2022 and April 2023. The study involved 21 semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, including healthcare administrators (6/21, 29%), occupational health and safety specialists (8/21, 38%), and healthcare workers (7/21, 33%). The stakeholders were asked about factors that influenced engagement with the DCT tool, acceptance at the organisational level, the implementation process, long-term use and sustainability of the DCT, and unintended consequences. Verbatim transcripts of the interviews were thematically analysed using NVivo (QSR International).
Hsiao et al. (2024)		X		The district-level public health authority developed and implemented a web-based application to assist aged care facilities in detecting and responding to influenza and COVID-19 outbreaks. This report discusses the challenges, drivers, and key lessons learned in the design and implementation of the app from the perspective of the public health practitioner (the author) who oversaw the project.

*Document Type:

A: Description, overall reflection, or theoretical perspective

B: Qualitative or quantitative research (involving primary data collection)

C: Content analysis

Study Focus: The Role of Digital Technologies in COVID-19 Surveillance

Key concepts from 14 studies have been analysed, highlighted, and compared in the role of digital technologies in COVID-19 surveillance (Table 4).

Table 4. The Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance

Authorship	Digital Technological Used	The Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance
Owusu (2020)	Digital technologies are employed to rapidly search and notify individuals potentially infected with COVID-19 through mobile software applications.	Digital technology is highlighted for its role in conducting quick searches and providing notifications for individuals potentially affected by COVID-19. The article argues that digital technology can complement or enhance traditional manual contact tracing methods. However, it emphasises the necessity of a strong regulatory framework to prevent misuse of individual information and ensure user privacy protection.
Chowdury et al. (2020)	<p>Digital technologies for contact tracing are used on smartphones. The technologies discussed include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Proximity Measurement Technology: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. GPS-based Distance Tracking b. Bluetooth-based Distance Tracking c. WiFi-based Positioning d. Cellular Network-based Location Calculation e. Other technologies and techniques 2. <i>Contact Tracing Protocols</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Temporary Contact Numbers (TCN) Protocol b. Epione – a decentralised contact tracing app supporting a novel protocol c. Multi-party Computation (MPC) Protocol d. Decentralised Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing (DP3T) e. Pan-European Privacy-Preserving Proximity Tracing (PEPP-PT) 	<p>The role of digital technology in using smartphones as contact tracing tools. Explicitly focusing on Proximity Measurement Technology and contact tracking protocols used for COVID-19 surveillance.</p> <p>Proximity Measurement Technology is designed to accurately detect human proximity, which is critical for planning and operations in various fields, including social sciences, architecture, and health. In COVID-19, maintaining a distance of 1.5 meters from infected individuals is critical, as sufficient exposure within this distance can lead to infection. Therefore, precisely estimating the distance between individuals and the duration of their exposure is crucial.</p> <p>Contact Tracing Protocols refer to methodologies used for effective contact tracing. This study discusses 12 different contact tracing protocols and compares them using the researcher’s taxonomy evaluation matrix.</p>

Authorship	Digital Technological Used	The Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance
	f. CAUDHT – decentralised peer-to-peer system for contact tracing g. QUEST Protocol h. PACT i. Blue Trace Protocol j. Whisper tracing Protocol k. The EPIC Protocol l. Recover Protocol	
Hayati et al (2021)	The Internet of Things (IoT) is a technological aid for infectious disease surveillance. The proof of concept involved adopting a reference model to design an IoT system for active digital surveillance of COVID-19.	The role of IoT in COVID-19 surveillance is to adopt an IoT reference model for active digital surveillance of COVID-19 disease. The use case for this design is a community-based surveillance system that utilises IoT to detect early symptoms and prevent close contact with COVID-19 in nursing homes.
Ummer et al. (2021)	35 digital health solutions were being used in Kerala, India, 5 of which are being used for COVID-19 surveillance purposes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. BeSafe Tracking 2. COVID Safety 3. COVID-19 Jagratha 4. GoK Dashboard 5. Kerala Health Disease Surveillance 	Five digital solutions play a key role in contact tracing. They use digital technology to track a person's position using the Global Positioning System (GPS). These solutions also alert people when they are near someone with a confirmed case of the virus. GPS, as digital surveillance for people infected with COVID-19, displays COVID-19 surveillance data (daily reports on COVID-19 status, quarantine reports, test results, and hotspots) and is a digital surveillance app using mobile phone location.
Unruh et al (2021)	Video technology can enhance case interviews, identify COVID-19 contacts, and determine exposure risks in temporary juvenile detention centers.	The role of video technology in COVID-19 surveillance includes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Immediate identification of close contacts, facilitating prompt recommendations for testing, medical isolation, and quarantine. 2. Providing 360° video coverage of an individual's route and location for up to 30 days before identification simplifies the detection of close contacts requiring surveillance. 3. Detailed identification of each exposure incident, including

Authorship	Digital Technological Used	The Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance
		observation of employee compliance with recommended infection control practices and quantification of exposure duration using video timestamps.
Baik and Eugene (2022)	The seven contact tracing apps in the United States are: 1. Care 19 Diary 2. Healthy Together 3. COVID WISE 4. Care 19 Alert 5. Guide Safe 6. Covid Watch 7. Covid Trace	The role of these apps in COVID-19 surveillance is as digital contact tracing tools launched on the App Store and Google Play for use on smartphones.
Geng and John (2022)	The role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance for case finding, contact tracing, and monitoring COVID-19 patients during the COVID-19 outbreak.	The role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance for case finding, contact tracing, and monitoring COVID-19 patients during the COVID-19 outbreak.
Sayibu, Jianxun, Tosin, Olatemi, et al. (2022)	Surveillance technology utilising mobile thermometer detectors, knowledge of the app, and self-mastery serves as a body temperature sensing tool to mitigate the risk of COVID-19.	The role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance includes providing notifications when a person with a high body temperature is detected, indicating a potential COVID-19 infection. This allows further surveillance and management to be carried out effectively.
Sayibu, Jianxun, Akintunde, et al. (2022)	Mobile Digital Culture (MDC) and advances in smartphone app technology are essential in surveillance, control, and tracking potential virus hotspots among high-risk populations.	The role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance includes as a tool for contact tracing and monitoring patients diagnosed with COVID-19. Factors such as mobile phone usability, knowledge of apps, and Mobile Digital Culture (MDC) were statistically significant in contributing to COVID-19 mitigation efforts.
Surio et al. (2022)	The following topics are discussed about digital technology: 1. National Electronic Disease Surveillance System Base System (NBS) 2. Sara Alert 3. REDCap, 4. Maven.	This article discusses various tools for surveillance systems, case investigation, proximity technology/exposure notification, contact tracing, and symptom tracking/monitoring. In addition, the article also highlights how public health officials and their informatics leaders are referencing information

Authorship	Digital Technological Used	The Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance
		on digital tools implemented by their peers to guide and refine their implementation plans.
Louw (2023)	The digital technologies discussed are the official websites of the Japanese and German governments. In Japan, well-known tools include a short-range tracing application (COVID-19 Contact-Confirming Application [COCOA]) and an outbreak management tool (Health Centre Real-time Information-sharing System on COVID-19 [HER-SYS]), which comes with an integrated symptom tracking tool (My HER-SYS). In Germany, tools developed include a short-range tracking application (Corona-Warn-App) and an outbreak management system (Surveillance Outbreak Response Management and Analysis System [SORMAS]).	The role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance includes being a contact tracing tool, integrating symptom tracking, facilitating distance tracking, and supporting overall COVID-19 management. Data collected through these technologies is stored in databases that governments can use to inform policy decisions during the COVID-19 outbreak.
Roberts and Ilan (2023)	Digital technology tracks infections, hospitalisations, deaths from COVID-19, and potential exposure to the SARS-Cov-2 virus.	The tool collects contact tracing data and tracks COVID-19 infections, hospitalisation rates, and deaths. The government uses this data to make decisions regarding COVID-19 management.
O'Dwyer et al. (2024)	Health systems have used Digital Contact Tracing (DCT) as an infection control strategy for healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic.	Contact tracing devices are used to monitor exposure and symptoms in healthcare workers.
Hsiao et al. (2024)	A web-based application to detect and respond to influenza and COVID-19 outbreaks in aged care facilities.	The app enables early detection of influenza and COVID-19 symptoms in older people within care facilities, allowing for timely surveillance and management. It can also be used to track contacts in case of COVID-19 infection among residents.

Discussion

Role of Digital Technology in COVID-19 Surveillance

Digital technology has become a crucial component in supporting COVID-19 surveillance. During the COVID-19 pandemic, various digital technologies have been utilised for public health

surveillance worldwide. However, there are still concerns about the rapid development and deployment of digital technologies, their use, and their efficacy in supporting public health goals. Digital technologies such as digital contact tracing tools (e.g., mobile phone apps, mobile phone tracking) reduce the spread of COVID-19.

Based on a synthesis of various articles, the primary roles of digital technologies include contact tracing, digital surveillance, symptom monitoring, outbreak management, infection control, and epidemiological data collection and analysis. In contact tracing, technologies such as Proximity Measurement Technologies (GPS, Bluetooth, WiFi, and cellular networks) facilitate tracking of individual locations and interactions. Protocols like DP3T and PEPP-PT are designed to protect user privacy during the tracing process. Additionally, applications such as COCOA in Japan, the Corona-Warn-App in Germany, and several apps in the United States (including Care 19 Diary and Healthy Together) provide real-time exposure notifications and assist users in managing their risk (Chowdhury et al., 2020).

Based on the existing literature, IoT-based technologies play a significant role in detecting early symptoms and preventing close contact (Hayati et al., 2021). Web-based applications also support early detection of influenza and COVID-19 symptoms in elderly care facilities (Hsiao et al., 2024). These technologies aid in case detection and provide crucial data for informed decision-making. Systems such as HER-SYS in Japan, SORMAS in Germany, and the Gok Dashboard in India facilitate the integration of contact tracing data, symptom tracking, and pandemic management. Additionally, tools like REDCap and Maven are employed for case investigation and symptom monitoring (Surio et al., 2022).

Digital technologies play a strategic role in epidemiological data collection and analysis. Digital Mobile Technologies monitor patients and track case locations in healthcare facilities (Geng & John, 2022). Additionally, some digital technologies empower governments to make more timely and effective data-driven decisions in pandemic management (Roberts & Ilan, 2023). These innovations have complemented traditional approaches to COVID-19 surveillance. However, their implementation must be supported by a robust regulatory framework to ensure user privacy and bolster public confidence in using these technologies. Some of these current studies illustrate the role of digital technology in COVID-19 surveillance, including locating cases, contact tracing and monitoring COVID-19 patients during the COVID-19 outbreak (Louw, 2023; Surio et al., 2023; Sayibu et al., 2022).

The Challenges of Digital Technology Implementation

Digital technology plays a significant role in COVID-19 surveillance, accelerating case detection, contact tracing, symptom monitoring, and real-time epidemiological data management. These technologies enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of surveillance compared to traditional methods and facilitate data-driven decision-making for improved pandemic management. Various innovations, including smartphone-based applications, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, video technology, and integrated surveillance systems, demonstrate the flexibility and diversity of technology in addressing surveillance needs across different contexts and regions.

Video technology can help with case interviews, identify people who have come into contact with someone infected with the virus, and assess the risks of exposure in a large juvenile temporary detention centre. The researchers developed a plan for managing a virus outbreak, which includes setting up a team to manage the epidemic and improving infection control through video surveillance (Unruh et al., 2021).

There are several barriers to the successful implementation of digital technologies in public health, including access to high-quality, unbiased data, issues related to technology and human resources, physical and network infrastructure, security and ethics, as well as various political, social, and environmental concerns. However, the successful implementation of these technologies relies heavily on a regulatory framework that safeguards user privacy, the reliability of the technology used, and public acceptance of these digital innovations. With proper management, digital technology is an essential tool during the COVID-19 pandemic and the foundation for developing a more robust surveillance system in the future.

Limitations

This study has several limitations, including its reliance solely on the SCOPUS database, which may exclude relevant research from other sources. Additionally, the study only considered peer-reviewed journal articles, thereby ignoring books, conference proceedings, and grey literature. Furthermore, resource limitations further narrowed the scope of the search.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Digital technologies play a critical role in COVID-19 surveillance, offering innovative solutions for contact tracing, symptom monitoring, infection tracking, and real-time data management. From smartphone-based apps and decentralised contact tracing protocols to IoT-based systems and video monitoring, each technology contributes significantly to detecting, preventing, and controlling the spread of COVID-19. Additionally, digital tools such as web-based applications, outbreak management systems, and proximity tracking technologies have demonstrated their ability to improve the efficiency and accuracy of surveillance efforts at both community and health institution levels.

However, the adoption of these digital technologies is not without its challenges. There is an urgent need for a strong regulatory framework to protect user privacy, ensure data security, and encourage public adoption of these technologies. The success of technology integration depends on the synergy between technological advancements, supportive policies, and people's digital literacy. Overall, digital technologies are tools and the foundation for creating a more responsive, adaptive, and data-driven health surveillance system. The experience from the COVID-19 pandemic provides valuable lessons in utilising technology to mitigate global health risks, ultimately helping to reduce the impact of future outbreaks.

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